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Effects of Peer Tutoring Strategy on Performance in Basic Science among Upper Basic Secondary School Students in Makurdi Metropolis

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of peer tutoring on academic performance of upper basic science students in Makurdi metropolis. Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were used to sample 65 (30 Male and 35 Female) students in two intact classes from the population of 1726 (828 Male and 898 Female) upper basic II students during 2023/2024 academic session in 25 government approved public secondary schools under Benue State Universal Basic Education Board, Makurdi. Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT), with reliability coefficient of 0.86 was determined using Kuder Richardson (KR-21) formula was used for data collection. Data were analysed using mean and standard deviation, mean gain scores and mean gain difference to answer research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using two-way analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Findings of the study showed that there is significant difference in performance mean scores of upper basic science students taught basic science using peer tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among others. Based on the findings, it was concluded that peer tutoring strategy enhance upper basic science students performance without gender disparity. Therefore, it was recommended that peer tutoring strategy should be encouraged at basic education level.

Keywords: Peer tutoring, Performance, Basic science and Gender

Introduction

The inclusiveness of Basic science as a core subject to be offered at lower, middle and upper basic level of education as enshrine in the national policy on education is to exposure the young learners to the world of science and technology so as to prepare them to meet up contemporary issues they may be facing in their daily activities.

Basic science (BS) is not a term that cannot be pinned down to a precise definition, Okworo (2002) as cited in Agogo and Ode (2017) sees BS as a course study which presents science discipline in all ramifications or diversity, in a unit whole so as to appreciate the interdependence of all science disciplines. According to the authors, the knowledge gained is relevant for man's comfortable living in his environment. Agogo and Ode (2011) refereed to it as a subject in which concepts and principles of science are presented so as to express the fundamental unity of scientific though and to avoid premature or undue stress on distinctions among the science fields.

The importance of Basic science and technology to national development in the life of any country cannot be overemphasized as the revised Curriculum of Basic Science and Technology (2012) has spelt out its importance as it is expected to enable the learners: develop interest in science and technology; acquire basic knowledge in science and technology; apply scientific and technological knowledge and skills to meet contemporary societal needs, take advantage of the numerous career opportunities provided by science and technology; become prepared for further studies in science and technology, avoid drug abuse and related vices; and be safety and security conscious. In spite of the importance of Basic Science, the performance of students is reported to poor in recent years.

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An analysis of students' performance in Basic Science from 2019 to 2022 at Basic Certificate Education Examination (BECE) shows a steady increase in failure rate from 3.72% in 2019, 8.97% in 2020 to 10.18% in 2021 and 8.46% in 2022 (Benue State Examination Board, 2023).

Several reasons have been advanced by researchers on the persistent poor performance in Basic Science reported by Ozaji as cited in Peni, (2016) identified factors responsible for the poor performance of learners in Basic science to (among others) include the followings: learner's inability to interact directly with learning materials; wrong perception of science by the learners and, fundamentally, the instructional strategy employed by teachers; all of which could be addressed by the use of peer-tutoring instructional strategy. In most educational organizations however, the instructional method consistently employed by science teachers is the lecture method (Obiekwe, 2008). This method of teaching places emphasis on memorization of facts which would only appeal to learners with well-developed reasoning abilities and intelligence. According to Marvel, Magnolia, Brillante and Laureano (2018) true learning means that the information that is presented and the skills that are acquired can be used throughout life, he believes that teachers should insist on learning activities linked to the real world.

Effective and appropriate implementation of students centred instructional methods such peer tutoring, fish born, thinking maps, and role play among others strategies could help improve Basic Science students' academic performance.

Peer-tutoring otherwise known as peer mentoring or peer assisted learning strategy is an effective and affordable way of providing students with academic and personal support from other students (Jibrin, Ibrahim & Zayum, 2016). In peer-tutoring technique, a higher performing student is paired with a lower one to review critical academic or behavioural concepts. Peer mentoring improves the learning experiences of both the tutors and tutees. When peer tutors participate in these schemes, they not only improve their own understanding of the subject areas, they also develop important communication and teamwork skills (Adamu & Kusa, 2018). Consequently, it has been argued that peer-tutoring learning strategy improves the academic achievement of students. In a quest to improve the general performance of students, Wael (2014) suggested the used of peer-tutoring strategy.

According to Tran (2014) peer-tutoring method does not only increase the performance of students, but also promotes their communication abilities and interpersonal relationships. Usually shy children learn effectively through tutoring by sharing their thoughts with classmates (Bombardelli, 2016). Peer-tutoring is an active teaching methodology that fosters student inclusion while enabling students to learn from each other (Cockerill, Craig & Thurston, 2018). These interactions between tutors and tutees promote active learning and foster student inclusion, as all students participate in the process (Fung, Tan & Chen, 2018). Empirically, Ovie (2022) investigated the effect of peer tutoring instructional strategy on student's performance and attitude towards learning Chemistry. The findings revealed a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Chemistry using peer tutoring instructional strategy and those taught using conventional strategy, in favor of those taught using peer tutoring strategy. In a similar vein, Azeez, Omananyi, Kwasi, and Abuh (2022) examined the effect of Jigsaw and Peer-tutoring instructional strategies on students' achievement and interest in periodic table of elements. Findings of the study revealed that jigsaw and peer-tutoring instructional strategies have significant effect on students' academic achievement and interest in periodic Table of elements concept of chemistry. Also, gender and interest have no influence on the academic achievement of students exposed to Jigsaw and peer tutoring instructional strategies. More so, Samuel and Sambo (2019) examined the effect of peer tutoring and reversed jigsaw instructional strategies on senior secondary school science students' interest and achievement. Findings from the study revealed a significant difference between the achievement of Science students in Peer-Tutoring, Reversed Jigsaw instructional strategies and conventional Demonstration method in favour of the two innovative strategies. These results indicates that students centred strategies such as peer tutoring instructional strategies are more effective in enhancing Science students' performance than the conventional lecture or demonstration methods.

According to Emaikwu (2012), there is a drastic and constant reduction in the level of performance by science students especially, basic science in Nigeria. This is evident in the students' low learning outcomes in Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) and other examination bodies. Academic performance has been defined and explained by several authors. For instance, Ayua and Tartenger, 2020 defined Academic Performance as the level of students scholarly accomplishment in Basic science where high and low scores indicate good and poor achievement respectively. Toryem, (2021) sees academic performance as a measure of change in behavior of learners over a given period of instruction. The measure of student's cognitive and psychomotor domains of behavioral objectivities in the learning process is determined through performance test. Persistent low academic performance in general has been an issue of concern and discussion among researchers in the past decade (Samba 2019). This could be attributed to ineffective teaching methods adopted which according to Ode and Tartenger (2021) has negative implication on students' academic abilities.

According to Tatli and Ayas (2013), effective teaching and learning will foster students' performance in the following ways:

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- a. Models positive influences on students' performance;
- b. Improves the utilisation of psychomotor skills;
- c. Enhances students' self-confidence in tackling scientific problems;
- d. Increases students' engagement and participation in the learning;
- e. Visualises macro, micro, and symbolical level presentations of the experiment; and
- f. Provides a strategy that follows the procedural steps.

This study intended to use peer tutoring strategy to determine whether these performance attributes could be achieved in Basic Science classroom.

Another factor that plays an important role in learner's performance is gender. Gender is defined by Ugwu and Nwagbo (2019) as the socially or culturally constructed characteristics and roles which are ascribed to males and females in any society. Review of literature has shown inconsistency in the results of male and female students' academic performance in Basic Science and science at large (Tofi, Usman & Lakpini, 2021). For instance, Ovie (2022) investigated the effect of peer tutoring instructional plan on student's performance and attitude towards learning Chemistry. The study found that Male had less achievement than female student taught chemistry using of peer tutoring teaching approach. Alamri (2018) also found that female students performed better than the male students; conversely Tartenger, Omega and Enemariae (2023) study revealed that boys performed better than their female counterparts. While Ode and Tartenger (2021) found no significant difference between male and female students' performance scores, Oludipe (2012) also found that there is no statistical difference in academic achievement of students in respect to gender when exposed students centred strategies.

Students' low performance in Basic Science irrespective of gender is indications of the likelihood of a deficiency in instructional strategies used in Basic Science instruction and this shows all is not well with the way the subject is been taught/learnt. To motivate and enhance students' performance, the teachers needs to make science real and relevant by using teaching strategies that will enable students learn easily and effectively. It is against this backdrop that it is imperative to investigate the effect of peer tutoring strategy on Basic Science students' academic performance in Makurdi metropolis.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to find out the effectiveness of peer tutoring instructional strategy on Basic Science Students' Academic Performance in Makurdi metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to:

- 1) determine if there is a difference in the mean academic performance scores of students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method
- 2) compare the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring instructional strategy.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. What is the mean scores difference between students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method?
- ii. What is the mean score difference between male and female students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy?

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant mean scores difference between students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring and those taught using lecture method.
2. There is no significant mean scores difference between male and female students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy

Methodology

The study adopted pre-test, post-test non-equivalent control group, quasi experimental research design. The population of the study consisted of the 1726 (828 male and 898 female) Upper basic II students out of the 25 Government approved public secondary schools during the 2023/2024 academic session in Makurdi, Benue State under Benue State Universal Basic Education Board Makurdi. A sample of 65 (30 Male and 35 Female) upper-Basic II Students in two schools was drawn from the population using purposive and random sampling. The instruments used for data collection was Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT). The instrument had 30 objective questions with 4 options (A, B, C and D). Each question had one correct answer and three distracters. The BSPT was used for pre-test and post-test on both control and experimental groups. The research

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instrument was validated by two experts in Department of Science and Mathematics Education of Benue State University, Makurdi, their inputs helped in improving the quality of the instrument. The reliability coefficient of BSPT was determined using Kuder Richardson (KR-21) on 30 students which were part of the population but not part of the sample for the study which yielded a reliability index of 0.86. The Data was collected with the help of two research assistants from the sampled schools. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation Whereas, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypothesis at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Results are presented according to order of research questions and hypotheses:

Research Question One

What is the mean scores difference between students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Academic Performance Scores of students taught Basic Science using Peer tutoring Strategy and those taught using lecture method.

S/No	Method	N	Pre –test		Post-test		Mean gain	Decision
			Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev		
1	Peer tutoring	34	7.55	2.273	13.92	5.310	6.37	In favour of peer tutoring strategy
2	Lecture	31	7.61	2.530	11.94	4.174	4.33	
Mean difference							2.04	

(Source: Field work, 2024)

The data in Table 1 shows the difference in the mean academic performance scores students’ taught Basic Science using Peer tutoring Strategy and those taught using lecture method. Data in the table also reveals that the mean gain of students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy is 6.37 and those taught using lecture method is 4.33. The difference in the mean Academic performance scores of the students’ taught is 2.04. in favour of students taught using peer tutoring strategy.

Research Question Two

What is the mean score difference between male and female students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy (PTS)?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female Students’ taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy (PTS).

S/NO	GenderPTS	Pre –test		Post-test		Mean gain	Decision	
		Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev			
1	Male	7.00	2.828	14.27	3.495	7.27	In favour of female students	
2	Female	7.50	2.542	15.74	4.929	8.24		
Mean difference							0.97	

(Source: Field work, 2024)

The data in Table 2 shows the difference in the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students’ taught Basic Science using peer tutoring. Data in the table further reveals the mean gain of male students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy as 7.27 and those of female students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy as 8.24, The difference in the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students’ taught Basic Science using peer tutoring is 0.97 in favour of female students.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant mean scores difference between students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring and those taught using lecture method.

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Table 3: ANCOVA of Academic performance scores of students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring and those taught using lecture method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	291.371 ^a	2	145.686	6.502	.003	.173
Intercept	663.766	1	663.766	29.623	.000	.323
Pretest	57.244	1	57.244	2.555	.115	.040
Method	239.601	1	239.601	10.693	.002	.147
Error	1389.244	62	22.407			
Total	14281.000	65				
Corrected Total	1680.615	64				

a. R Squared = .173 (Adjusted R Squared = .147)

(Source: field work 2024)

The data in Table 3 reveals that $F(1,62) = 10.693$; $p = 0.002 < 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis which state that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of students taught Basic Science using Peer tutoring Strategy and those taught using lecture method is not retained. This implies that there is significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of students' exposed to Peer tutoring Strategy and those taught exposed to lecture method. The partial Eta square of 0.147 was obtained for method meaning that only 14.7% of the Basic Science performance scores can be accounted for the influence of instructional strategy/ method in Basic Science class when taught using Peer tutoring Strategy and those taught using lecture method.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant mean scores difference between male and female students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy

Table 4: ANCOVA of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female Students taught Basic Science using peer tutoring strategy.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	35.739 ^a	2	17.869	.619	.545	.038
Intercept	608.216	1	608.216	21.070	.000	.405
Pretest	.955	1	.955	.033	.857	.001
Gender	32.218	1	32.218	1.116	.299	.035
Error	894.879	31	28.867			
Total	9349.000	34				
Corrected Total	930.618	33				

a. R Squared = .038 (Adjusted R Squared = -.024)

(Source: field work 2024)

The data in Table 4 reveals that $F(1,31) = 1.116$; $p = 0.299 > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis state that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught using peer tutoring strategy is retained. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught using peer tutoring strategy. The partial Eta square of 0.035 was obtained for gender meaning that only 3.5% of the Basic Science performance scores can be accounted for the influence of gender in Basic Science class when taught using peer tutoring.

Discussion of Findings

Finding from hypothesis one showed that there is significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of students' taught using Peer tutoring Strategy and those taught using lecture. The students exposed to peer tutoring strategy outperformed their counterparts exposed to lecture method. This finding agrees with Ovie (2022) whom investigated the effect of peer tutoring instructional strategy on student's performance and attitude towards learning Chemistry and found a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Chemistry using peer tutoring instructional strategy and those taught using conventional strategy, more so Azeez, Omananyi, Kwasi, and Abuh (2022) also found a significant different in students' achievement and interest in periodic table of elements when taught using peer tutoring and conventional method. The finding is also in line with that of Samuel and Sambo (2019) whom examined the

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effect of peer tutoring and reversed jigsaw instructional strategies on senior secondary school science students' interest and achievement and found a significant difference among the strategies when compared with conventional methods.

This finding may be possible because peer tutoring strategy provide equal opportunities to both fast and slow learners students as it has been reported to be a useful tool for helping students with the process of building conceptual understanding of disciplinary content and consequently, promoting their performance which made it possible for the students in peer tutoring strategy to attained high performance.

The finding from hypothesis two indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught using peer tutoring strategy. This implies that the performance of both male and female students exposed to peer tutoring strategy is enhanced. This agrees with Ode and Tartenger (2021) who found no significant difference between male and female students' performance scores. Oludipe (2012) also found that there is no statistical difference in academic achievement of students in respect to gender when exposed to students-centred strategies. This high and gender free performance could be a result of the involvement of students' active participation in the class as every student's is given an opportunity to make their contribution during group discussions, the intelligent and even the slow learners. Conversely however, this finding disagreed with the findings of Alamri (2018) who found that female students performed better than the male students and Tartenger, Omega and Enemariae (2023) study revealed that boys performed better than their female counterparts.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained in the study, the researchers concluded that, the use of peer tutoring strategy enhance students' academic performance in basic science than the conventional lecture method. Peer tutoring strategy of teaching is also gender friendly.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of this study it was recommended that;

- i. Basic science students should be encouraged to serve as tutors to teach their colleagues various concepts in basic science especially during tutorial classes.
- ii. Peer tutoring strategy should be use by basic science teachers at basic education level to enhance Basic Science students' academic performance since the strategy is gender friendly.

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